

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Utilitarian, hedonic, privacy and trust on online purchase intentions mediated by attitude toward online purchasing

Muslikhun, Wulandari Harjanti and Tri Wahjoedi *

Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Mahardhika, Surabaya, Indonesia.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2022, 14(03), 054–067

Publication history: Received on 26 April 2022; revised on 31 May 2022; accepted on 02 June 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2022.14.3.0502>

Abstract

E-commerce is another option for buying goods in modern society. Indonesia is a country that has very fast e-commerce growth. Online purchases need to have a positive attitude towards e-commerce in order to influence consumers' online purchase intent to use e-commerce. Many factors, such as utility value, hedonic value, privacy, and trust, determine a positive attitude of a consumer. The purpose of this study is to investigate the utility value, hedonic value, privacy, trust impact on online purchase behavior, and the impact of online purchase behavior on online purchase intent. The survey was conducted on 100 Lazada users in Surabaya City. The data was collected by directly distributing surveys to respondents using targeted sampling techniques. Analytical technology uses SEMPLS. The results show that the utilitarian value, the hedonic value, privacy, and trust had a significant positive impact on attitudes towards online purchases, and attitudes towards online purchases also had a significant positive impact on the intent of online purchases. This study enriches information related to the relationship among utilitarian, hedonic, privacy and trust in attitude toward online purchasing and online purchase intentions.

Keywords: Hedonic Value; Online Purchasing; Privacy; Trust; Utilitarian Value

1. Introduction

Understanding Technology and information (IT) is advancing and developing so rapidly in the era of globalization. The number of internet users in Indonesia is increasing from year to year, which causes the advancement and development of internet technology. Official data from the Indonesian Internet Service Providers Association (APJII) can prove an increase in the number of Internet users, which shows data on the growth rate of Internet users in Indonesia.

With internet, business people do business online or commonly referred to as e-commerce. E-commerce is the use of conversation networks and computers to perform commercial enterprise approaches. A famous view of e-commerce is the use of the internet and computers with net browsers used to buy and promote merchandise [1]. Today, e-commerce is another option for buying goods in modern society. Indonesia is the fastest growing e-commerce country in the world. In recent years, more and more business people, whether large companies or retail companies, have changed or expanded their business to digital.

One of the biggest e-commerce in Indonesia is Lazada. Lazada became launched in March 2012 and has grown very hastily so far. Lazada Indonesia is part of the Lazada institution's online retail community, which operates in six international locations/regions in Southeast Asia. This includes Lazada in Indonesia, Malaysia, Thailand, Vietnam, Singapore and the Philippines, with a total of 550 million customers from six countries.

* Corresponding author: Tri Wahjoedi
Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Mahardhika, Surabaya, Indonesia.

Lazada is engaged in online trading and e-commerce retail. Lazada is the result of the development of Rocket Internet, a German Internet technology incubator company. Rocket Internet has also succeeded in creating innovative and creative companies around the world headquartered in Berlin, Germany. Lazada Indonesia pays more attention to B2C or business-to-customer e-commerce, because the company's main goal is to attract individual customers who make transactions on its website. "Business to Customer" pays more attention to how the basic mechanism for buyers to access the company is processed on the network provided by the company.

Lazada has the most fans among its competitors which is 16,906,030. Tokopedia ranks second with 3,738,706 followers, followed by blibli.com with 2,626,450 followers. It can be concluded that people trust and like shopping or browsing on Lazada. These followers come from consumers who want to get new information about Lazada and learn about the promotions that are currently available. The number of shopping centers in Surabaya does not dampen the interest of consumers to buy goods online. Adjustments in human being's behavior in e-commerce is a task confronted by way of businesses a good way to meet the desires and goals of customers. [2] shows that selling via the internet can also make it easy for customers no longer to need to struggle with site visitors, no longer need to look for a parking space, and stroll from keep to keep.

There are two values that affect consumer satisfaction, among which consumers will consider the benefits (utilitarian value) provided by the product when making a purchase. Consumer behavior guided by utilitarian values will choose or buy products with rational reasons [3]. In contrast to the hedonic value, because when consuming a product, experiencing and consuming a product is related to the five senses that have an effect on one's emotions, along with sensation, delusion, satisfaction. The hedonic value is based totally on the overall client evaluation based totally on pride and satisfaction [4].

One of the factors that have an effect on customer buying interest to make purchases via on-line media is consider. Customer consider in on-line purchasing can be interpreted as accept as true with in a particular item, inclusive of accept as true with in e-trade or consider in on-line sellers [5]. This trust is one of the important factors, and will make consumers interested in making purchases online.

In addition, in online shopping, privacy and security factors are also one of the important factors faced by e-commerce users. New e-commerce users are often confused when visiting websites and worry that user information that has been provided to e-commerce websites will be disseminated to the public. Therefore, by reducing concerns about the misuse of personal data and data transactions, ensuring data security is critical to building trust. If security is guaranteed and consumer expectations are met, consumers will be willing to disclose their personal information to sellers and buy with a sense of security.

Attitudes towards online purchasing can be defined as positive or negative consumer feelings related to the realization of buying behavior through the internet [6]. When consumers have a positive attitude towards e-commerce websites, consumers tend to show their willingness to search for product information through the website before deciding to buy.

According to [7], consumers who are already positive about a product or brand will be motivated to buy this product or brand. Interest in buying online is one of the most important factors in making purchases online because consumers with strong intentions often realize these intentions through the act of shopping online.

This research was conducted to determine the effect of utilitarian values, hedonic values, privacy and trust on online shopping attitudes and online purchase intentions of Lazada Surabaya. And partially analyses the effect of utilitarian values, hedonic values, privacy and trust on Lazada's online buying attitude and willingness to buy online. Therefore, the results of this study are expected to help develop knowledge about online purchase intentions in e-commerce and provide useful descriptions and information for companies to make decisions, policies, and marketing strategies that can be used for Lazada online marketing in Surabaya, taking into account the impact of values on utilitarian variables, hedonic values, privacy, trust, and attitudes towards online purchasing and online purchase intention attitudes.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Theoretical basis

2.1.1. Utilitarian values

The practical value is the consumer's evaluation of the product's functional attributes. [8] reveals another point of view, which shows that utilitarian values are a person's encouragement to evaluate motivation and time and energy efficiency

to obtain quality products and/or services [9]. Consumer behavior oriented to utilitarian values will choose products based on rationality and efficiency Holbrook and Hirschman in [10].

[11] believes that utilitarian values have two dimensions, namely efficiency and achievement:

- Efficiency can be understood as consumer needs in terms of saving time and resources.
- Achievement can be understood as finding a product that has been planned in advance to achieve the shopping goal.

2.1.2. Hedonic value

Hedonic value is described as the overall evaluation of customers based totally on delight and pleasure. Hedonic value is related to the pride or aesthetic awareness of the product. Hedonic stimulus is a stimulus that chooses the quality of the purchasing surroundings based on perceived leisure, visible enchantment and escape [8].

Arnold and Reynolds mention in [11] six dimensions to measure the level of consumer hedonic, namely: adventure, social interaction, satisfaction, ideas, roles and values.

- Shopping adventure
- Consumers shop because of experience, and consumers feel they have got their own world through shopping.
- Social shopping
- Consumers will find this true and will enjoy the purchase after the customer spends time with family and friends. There are also customers who suppose that purchasing is a sort of social interest, whether or not it's miles between purchasers or employees who work in branches. consumers additionally count on that by way of shopping with family or buddies, customers get a number of statistics about the products they need to shop for.
 - Satisfied shopping
 - Shopping is another option for reducing stress and dealing with bad problems, and it's also a way to forget the problems.
 - Creative shopping
 - Clients shop to maintain up with new style traits and spot new merchandise or items. normally because of seeing commercials furnished through mass media.
 - Shop for characters
 - Consumers select to shop for others than for themselves, so purchasers sense drawn to shopping for others.
 - High value shopping
 - When consumers bargain, or when they are looking for places to shop that offer discounts, discounts, or places to shop at low prices, consumers think that shopping is a game.

2.1.3. Privacy

Privacy is generally defined as the ability of an character to receive, control, and use personal data [12]. Therefore, in the context of the Internet, privacy involves aspects such as distribution, such as obtaining or using personal information. At the same time, the perception of privacy is related to consumers' ability to control the dissemination of information or consumer behavior of others around them during transactions. According to [13] Perceived privacy is the possibility for online companies to collect and use personal data incorrectly. Therefore, when a website requests such information, customers are reluctant to enter their personal information because they are concerned about the collection and misuse of information transmitted over the Internet and how their data will be used. The impact is that online consumers are reluctant to disclose their personal or financial information to companies because they believe that companies can use this information without permission or disclose it to other organizations. Armesh and the others expressed a more positive understanding. According to [14], privacy in e-trade is described as the willingness to share statistics via the net to attain a purchase. Therefore, the characteristics that need to be evaluated in the privacy attribute are:

- Use of privacy statement.
- Company policy in selling customer information to third parties.
- Use trackers to collect personal information.

2.1.4. Trust

[15] argues that consumer trust is all the knowledge that consumers have, and all the conclusions that consumers draw about objects, characteristics, and interests. The purpose here is in the form of products, people, businesses, and anything that someone believes the product is comfortable and friendly, and it is not easy to abandon the product or replace it with another brand of product. Therefore, the brand also plays an important role in becoming the identity of the product. A brand must be able to give confidence to consumers that the brand can really be trusted. Through the building of a trust by a company, potential consumers will be sure that the products issued by the company will be able to meet their needs and desires.

According to [11] Three factors that shape one's trust in others, namely ability, kindness and integrity. These factors can be explained as follows:

Ability

Functionality refers to the capacity and characteristics of the seller/organization to persuade and authorize a specific area. In this example, how the vendor presents, serves and protects transactions from interference from other parties. Competence includes capability, experience, institutional reputation and scientific prowess.

Charity

Goodwill is the seller's willingness to provide mutually beneficial satisfaction between himself and the consumer. Sellers not only pursue profit maximization, but also focus on achieving customer satisfaction. Kindness includes caring, empathy, confidence, and acceptance.

Integrity

Integrity relates to the behaviour or conduct of the vendor when engaging in commercial enterprise. Is the first-class of the goods sold dependable? Integrity may be visible from the perspective of fairness, performance, loyalty, honesty, and reliability.

2.1.5. Attitude towards online purchasing

[16] show that attitude is an expression of deep emotion, which reflects a person's interest or disinterest in a particular object (such as a brand or service). In addition, it is emphasized that attitude is a kind of learning tendency, and the pattern of behavior is always active or inactive for a particular object.

[17] show that attitudes provide a relatively consistent description of a person's evaluation, feelings, and tendencies towards an object or idea. Attitude puts a person in a mental state of liking or disliking something, approaching or leaving something. Attitude is a person's view of something. This can be a product, advertisement, salesperson, company, or idea. Attitude is an important topic for marketers because it influences the selection, learning, and final buying decisions that people make.

[18] states that consumer attitudes are important factors that influence consumer decision making. The concept of attitude is closely related to the concept of belief and behavior.

[16] mention the pose component based on the three-component pose model. The attitudes of the three main components are:

- Cognitive components, knowledge and perception are obtained based on a combination of direct experience and perception, combined with direct experience objects and attitudes, as well as related information from various sources.
- The emotional component. The emotions and feelings of consumers towards certain products or brands are the emotional components of certain attitudes.
- The intentional component refers to the possibility or tendency of individuals to take special actions or behave in certain ways towards certain attitude objects.

2.1.6. Online purchase intention

Purchase intentions can arise when consumers think of motivation in their minds, and thus become a desire. If there is no process, there is no motivation to make it happen. With this process, the consumer's dietary motivation will become a reality. A person's strong desire will eventually be fulfilled [19].

Online purchase intentions can be affected by changes in technology. Where, now a person can easily meet their needs. With technology, people don't need to bother going out of the house, but as long as they are at home, people can shop online [20].

In general, intention can be defined as the desire to do what you want to do or like to do. Online purchase intention is a transaction made by someone to fulfil their needs. Purchase intention is a plan made by consumers to buy goods or services in the future. In other words, consumers can contemplate the many products or services they plan to purchase using the Internet.

Source: processed by researchers

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

Research Hypothesis

Based on the formulation of the problem and empirical studies that have been carried out previously, the hypotheses proposed in this study are:

- H1: Utilitarian values influence attitude toward online purchasing
- H2: Hedonic value influences attitude toward online purchasing
- H3: Privacy influences attitude toward online purchasing
- H4: Trust influences attitude toward online purchasing
- H5: Attitude toward online purchasing influences online purchase intention

3. Methods

This is quantitative research which the survey data is in numerical format and the analysis uses statistics [21]. Quantitative approach is an approach that is based on the measurement of the variables of a subject. A quantitative approach is used to determine the perception of the research sample on the research model that has been made.

In this study the independent variable (X) is Utilitarian value, Hedonic value, Privacy, Trust, the intervening variable (Z) in this study is Attitude toward online purchasing while the dependent variable (Y) is Online purchase intention. The data sources used in this study are the primary data sources. The key data for this survey was obtained directly from Lazada users in Surabaya through the distribution of questionnaires.

The population in this take a look at is the humans of Surabaya who've completed on line shopping on the Lazada application in Surabaya. The pattern on this examine is some of the humans of Surabaya who have shopped online at the Lazada application.

Considering a large, unknown population, the minimum sampling method refers to the following concepts [22] for the sample in the multivariate assessment, we will use 5 times more diverse parameters (indicators) obtained using 95 respondents (5 x 19 indicators). In this consideration, the pattern used was changed to 100 respondents. Because it has exceeded the minimum number of samples, the sample with 100 people has met the research requirements.

This research uses structural model analysis using Partial Least Square, where this model is a component based or variance based predictive model. The SEM PLS analysis technique is a form of soft modelling, which does not focus on the criteria of measurement scale, data distribution, and strict sample size.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Descriptive Test

The assessment of each research variable was ranked based on an interval scale according to its average value. The interval scale calculation is as follows:

Interval scale = (Highest score – Lowest score)/Number of scales

Interval scale = (5 – 1)/5 = 0.8

The rating value category for each variable according to the interval scale can be seen in Table 1;

Table 1 Rating Category Based on Scale

Variables	1.10-1.80	1.81-2.60	2.61-3.40	3.41-4.20	4.21-5.00
Utilitarian (X1)	Very low	Low	High enough	High	Very high
Hedonic (X2)	Very low	Low	High enough	High	Very high
Privacy (X3)	Very low	Low	High enough	High	Very High
Trust (X4)	Very low	Low	High enough	High	Very high
Attitude toward online purchasing (Z)	Very bad	Bad	Pretty good	Good	Very good
Online purchasing intention (Y)	Very low	Low	High enough	High	Very high

Source: data processed by researchers

4.1.1. Description of the Utilitarian Variable (X1)

The description of the utilitarian variable (X1) can be seen through the average value for each utilitarian indicator in Table 2.

Table 2 Description of the Utilitarian Variable (X1)

Item	Indicators	Average	Evaluation
X1.1	Consumers complete shopping activities as desired in online shopping	3.57	High
X1.2	When consumers do online shopping, they can find the product they are looking for	3.72	High
X1.3	Consumers feel that their online shopping activities are successful	3.54	High
	Total Average	3.61	High

Source: data processed by researchers

Based on Table 2, it can be explained that the utilitarian indicator which has the last indication of the role in determining the utilitarian shopping style is that consumers feel their online shopping activities are successful, because they have the lowest average value, which is 3.54.

The utilitarian indicator that has an indication of the most important role in determining utilitarian shopping style is when consumers do online shopping can find the product they are looking for, which 3.72 is the highest.

The average value of the utilitarian shopping style (X1) as a whole is 3.61, which indicates the condition that the overall consumer utilitarian shopping style is in the high category.

4.1.2. Description of Hedonic Variables (X2)

The description of the hedonic variable (X2) can be seen through the average value for each hedonic indicator in Table 3:

Table 3 Description of hedonic variable (X2)

Item	Indicators	Average	Evaluation
X2.1	Consumers feel the excitement of searching when shopping online	3.60	High
X2.2	Consumers prefer to shop online for themselves, not just the products they want to buy	3.87	High
X2.3	Consumers shop online from desire, not inevitably	3.53	High
X2.4	When doing on line shopping, purchasers feel an experience of adventure	3.73	High
	Total Average	3.68	High

Source: data processed by researchers

Using Table 3, the hedonic index provides the final clue to its role in determining the hedonic shopping style, with the lowest mean of 3.53, online for fun rather than consumer needs.

The hedonic indicator which has an indication of the most important role in determining the hedonic shopping style is that consumers enjoy online shopping for their own interests not only for the products they will buy, because they have the highest average value, which is 3.87.

The average value of hedonic shopping style (X2) as a whole is 3.68, which indicates the condition that overall consumer utilitarian shopping style is in the high category.

4.1.3. Description of Privacy Variable (X3)

The description of the privacy variable (X3) can be seen through the average value for each privacy indicator in Table 4:

Table 4 Description of Privacy Variable (X3)

Item	Indicators	Average	Evaluation
X3.1	Security features for data exchange such as SSL (Secure Socket Layer) and others are important in consumer decisions to buy on online shopping sites	3.60	High
X3.2	Safeguarding the privacy of third parties is important in consumers' decisions to buy on online shopping sites	3.65	High
X3.3	The contents of the privacy policy statement are important in consumers' decisions to buy on online shopping sites	3.54	High
	Total Average	3.59	High

Source: data processed by researchers

Based on Table 4, it can be explained that the privacy indicator which has the last indication of the role in determining privacy is the content of the privacy policy statement which is important in consumer decisions to buy on online shopping sites, because it has the lowest average value, which is 3.54.

The privacy indicator that has an indication of the most important role in determining privacy is that third party privacy security is an important thing in consumer decisions to buy on online shopping sites, which 3.63 is the highest.

The average value of consumer privacy (X3) as a whole is 3.59, which indicates the condition that overall consumers state that the level of privacy on the Lazada shopping site is in the high category.

4.1.4. Description of Trust Variable (X4)

The description of the trust variable (X4) can be seen through the average value for each trust indicator in Table 5:

Table 5 Description of Trust Variable (X4)

Item	Indicators	Average	Evaluation
X4.1	Trustworthy and honest online shopping site	3.58	High
X4.2	Online shopping sites keep their promises and obligations	3.74	High
X4.3	Reliable online shopping site infrastructure	3.82	High
	Total Average	3.71	High

Source: data processed by researchers

Based on Table 5, it can be explained that the trust indicator which has the last indication of its role in determining trust is an online shopping site that can be trusted and honest, because it has the lowest average value, which is 3.58.

The trust indicator which has an indication of the most important role in determining trust is a reliable online shopping site infrastructure, which 3.82 is the highest.

The average value of trust (X4) of consumers as a whole is 3.71, which shows the condition that overall consumers have a level of trust in the Lazada shopping site which is included in the high category.

4.1.5. Description of the Attitude variable toward online purchasing (Z)

The description of the attitude toward online purchasing (Z) variable can be seen through the average value for each attitude toward online purchasing indicator in Table 6.

Table 6 Description of Variable Attitude toward online purchasing (Z)

Item	Indicators	Average	Evaluation
Z1	The idea of using an online site to shop for a product is an interesting thing	3.69	Good
Z2	Consumers like the idea of buying a product online	3.71	Good
Z3	Using the site to buy a product from a retail store is a good idea	3.94	Good
	Total Average	3.78	Good

Source: data processed by researchers

Based on Table 6, it can be explained that the indicator of attitude toward online purchasing which has the last indication of the role in determining consumer attitudes is the idea of using online sites to shop for a product which is interesting, which 3.69 is the highest.

The indicator of attitude toward online purchasing which has an indication of the most important role in determining consumer attitudes is that using a site to buy a product from a retail store is a good idea, because it has the highest average value, which is 3.94.

The average value of attitude toward online purchasing (Z) of consumers as a whole is 3.78, which indicates the condition that consumers have an attitude towards online shopping on the Lazada shopping site which is included in the good category.

4.1.6. Description of the Online Purchase Intention Variable (Y)

The description of the online purchase intention variable (Y) can be seen through the average value for each online purchase intention indicator in Table 7;

Table 7 Description of Variable Online purchase intention (Y)

Item	Indicators	Average	Evaluation
Y1	There is a strong desire that consumers will buy a product online in the future	3.75	High
Y2	Consumers will recommend online shopping to their friends	3.79	High
Y3	Consumers intend to use online shopping regularly for the next 1-2 years	3.90	High
	Total Average	3.81	High

Source: data processed by researchers

Based on Table 7, it can be explained that the online purchase intention indicator which has an indication of the most recent role in determining shopping intentions is that there is a strong desire that consumers will buy a product online in the future, because it has the lowest average value, which is 3.75. .

The online purchase intention indicator that has an indication of the most important role in determining shopping intentions is that consumers intend to use online shopping regularly for the next 1-2 years, which 3.90 is the highest.

The average value of online purchase intention (Y) of consumers as a whole is 3.81, which indicates the condition that overall consumers have online shopping intentions on the Lazada shopping site which is included in the high category.

4.2. Analysis Model

4.2.1. Analysis of the Measurement Model

Validity

Table 8 Results of Convergent Validity Test (Outer Loading Value)

Variables	Indicators	Loading Factor
Utilitarian (X1)	X1.1	0.8896
	X1.2	0.8924
	X1.3	0.8967
Hedonic (X2)	X2.1	0.8533
	X2.2	0.7417
	X2.3	0.8482
	X2.4	0.7855
Privacy (X3)	X3.1	0.8800
	X3.2	0.8749
	X3.3	0.8603
Trust (X4)	X4.1	0.7942
	X4.2	0.8227
	X4.3	0.8162
Attitude toward online purchasing (Z)	Z1	0.7681
	Z2	0.8383
	Z3	0.8423
Online purchase intention (Y)	Y1	0.8286
	Y2	0.8526
	Y3	0.7790

Source: data processed by researchers

To measure the validity of the PLS analysis, convergent validity and discriminant validity are used. Convergent validity is measured through the correlation between indicator items and construct scores or variables. If the outer loading value has a minimum value of 0.7, then the indicator is considered to have met the validity criteria.

Convergence validation shows that all load coefficients have values greater than 0.7 for each variable. This indicates that all indicators of the survey variable meet the convergence validity criteria.

Reliability

Reliability is measured by assessing combined reliability and Cronbach's alpha coefficient. Reliability shows a measure of the internal consistency of the indicator block for a variable [23]. If the Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha values have a minimum value of 0.70, the indicator block of a variable can be declared reliable. Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha analysis results for each variable can be seen in Table 9.

Table 9 Composite Reliability Analysis Results and Cronbach Alpha

Variables	Composite Reliability	Cronbach Alpha
Utilitarian (X1)	0.9219	0.8729
Hedonic (X2)	0.8827	0.8523
Privacy (X3)	0.9048	0.8423
Trust (X4)	0.8523	0.7406
Attitude toward online purchasing (Z)	0.8607	0.7572
Online purchase intention (Y)	0.8573	0.7507

Source: data processed by researchers

The analysis show that the Composite Reliability values and Cronbach Alpha values of each variable are utilitarian (X1), hedonic (X2), privacy (X3), trust (X4), attitude toward online purchasing (Z), and online purchase intention (Y). Indicates a value greater than 0.70, so the configuration of each variable is reliable.

The results of the Outer Model analysis can be described clearly as shown in Figure 2.

Source: processed by researchers

Figure 2 Outer Model Analysis Results

4.2.2. Structural Model Analysis

Collinearity Test

In PLS because the estimated path coefficient since the structural model is based on the OLS model (ordinary least squares), need to perform a co-linearity test when evaluating the structural model [22]. To evaluate the structural model there is a possibility of bias. If the level of collinearity is high then there is a possibility of bias in the estimation of the structural model. The evaluation of collinearity can be seen from the VIF value, if the VIF value is above the value of 5.00 then it is an indication of a collinearity condition. The results of the collinearity test analysis are shown in Table 10.

Table 10 Collinearity Testing the Effect of X1 and X2 on Y

Construct	VIF
Utilitarian (X1)	1.327
Hedonic (X2)	1.651
Privacy (X3)	1.998
Trust (X4)	2.472

Source: data processed by researchers

The results of this collinearity test mean that the VIFs of all predictor configurations are still below the cut-off value of 5.00. Therefore, we can conclude that there is no co-linearity between the predictor configurations of the structural model.

4.3. Structural Model

If the value of the t fact is greater than the vital factor value of the t table at 1.96, then the path factor can be said to have a significant impact. The test results are shown in Table 11.

Table 11 Test Results of the Significance of Path Coefficient (Path) Structural Model

Relation	Path Coefficient	t statistics	Information
X1 → Z	0.1795	2.4951	Significant
X2 → Z	0.2871	2.9783	Significant
X3 → Z	0.2310	2.4861	Significant
X4 → Z	0.3467	3.4506	Significant
Z → Y	0.5950	9.8695	Significant

Source: data processed by researchers

Testing the significance of the path coefficient through the t statistic test shows the following results:

- Based on the results of the analysis, it can be seen that the path coefficient value of the utilitarian influence (X1) on the attitude toward online purchasing (Z) is positive at 0.1795, with the t statistic value of 2.4951 > 1.96 (t table value). Shows that utilitarian (X1) has a significant positive effect on attitudes toward online purchasing (Z).
- The path coefficient value of hedonic influence (X2) on attitude toward online purchasing (Z) is positive at 0.2871, with t statistics value of 2.9783 > 1.96 (t table value). Shows that hedonic (X2) has a significant positive effect on attitudes toward online purchasing (Z).
- The path coefficient value of the influence of privacy (X3) on attitude toward online purchasing (Z) is positive 0.2310, with t statistics value of 2.4862 > 1.96 (t table value). Shows that privacy (X3) has a significant positive effect on attitudes toward online purchasing (Z).
- The path coefficient value of the influence of trust (X4) on attitudes toward online purchasing (Z) is positive at 0.3467, with a t statistics value of 3.4506 > 1.96 (t table value). Shows that trust (X4) has a significant positive effect on attitudes toward online purchasing (Z).

- The path coefficient value of the influence of attitude toward online purchasing (Z) on online purchase intention (Y) is positive at 0.5950, with t statistics value of 9.8695 > 1.96 (t table value). Shows that attitude toward online purchasing (Z) has a significant positive effect on online purchase intention (Y).

The results of the analysis of the structural model or inner model using the PLS method can be seen in Figure 3;

Source: processed by researchers

Figure 3 Inner Model Analysis Results

4.4. Hypothesis Testing

4.4.1. First Hypothesis Test

The value of utilitarian shopping affects online shopping attitudes. The analysis results show that the path factor is positive and the t-statistic value is 2.4951 > the t-table value is 1.96. This suggests that utilitarian (X1) has a significant positive effect on attitudes towards online purchasing (Z).

Therefore, the first hypothesis that the value of utilitarian shopping influences attitudes towards online shopping is accepted.

4.4.2. Second Hypothesis Test

The second hypothesis shows that the value of hedonic shopping influences attitudes towards online shopping. Based on the results of the analysis, we find that the path factor is positive with a statistical t-value of 2.9783 > a t-table value of 1.96. This suggests that hedonic (X2) has a significant positive effect on attitudes towards online purchasing (Z). Therefore, the second hypothesis that the value of pleasure shopping affects attitudes towards online shopping is accepted.

4.4.3. Third Hypothesis Test

The third hypothesis states that privacy has a negative effect on online shopping attitudes. Based on the results of the analysis, the path coefficients are positive and the statistical t-value is 2.4862 > table t-value is 1.96, suggesting that privacy (X3) has a significant positive effect on attitude toward online purchasing (Z). Therefore, the third hypothesis that privacy adversely affects online shopping attitude is accepted.

4.4.4. Fourth Hypothesis Test

The fourth hypothesis states that trust influences attitudes towards online shopping. Based on the results of the analysis, we can see that the path coefficients are positive and the statistical t-value is 3.4506 > the table t-value is 1.96. This suggests that trust (X4) has a significant positive effect on attitude toward online purchasing (Z). Therefore, the fourth hypothesis that trust affects online shopping attitudes is accepted.

4.4.5. Fifth Hypothesis Test

The fifth hypothesis states that the attitude of online shopping influences the intent of online shopping. Based on the results of the analysis, the pass factor is positive, the statistical t-value is 9.8695 > the table t-value is 1.96, indicating an attitude towards online purchasing (Z) have a significant positive effect on online shopping intentions (Y). Therefore, the fifth hypothesis that online shopping attitudes affect online shopping intentions, is accepted.

4.4.6. Managerial Implication

The results of this study enrich information related to the relationship among utilitarian, hedonic, privacy and trust in attitude toward online purchasing and online purchase intentions. The findings of this study can help conduct further research.

5. Conclusion and Suggestion

From the results of the analysis performed, can be concluded that:

- The value of utilitarian shopping on online shopping attitudes at Lazada Surabaya was found to be positive and significant.
- The value of hedonic shopping on online shopping attitudes at Lazada Surabaya was found to be positive and significant.
- Privacy on online shopping attitudes at Lazada Surabaya was found to be positive and significant.
- Trust in online shopping attitudes at Lazada Surabaya was found to be positive and significant.
- Online shopping attitudes towards online shopping intentions at Lazada Surabaya were found to be positive and significant

5.1. Suggestion

5.1.1. Academic Advice

The results of this study can be used as a reference for research on the relationship between the value of utilitarian spending, the value of hedonic spending, privacy and trust in influencing the company's products. In addition, for academics to continue this research by adding other variables that can influence.

5.1.2. Practical Advice

- Related to the value of utilitarian shopping, to increase the success rate of consumer shopping, the online store must provide clear information about the products sold, and complete the products according to the wishes of consumers. Ease of shopping and increased transactions will be able to add value to utilitarian shopping so that consumers will continue to make repeat purchases.
- Related to the value of hedonic shopping, designing shopping sites as attractive as possible, and always holding interesting shopping events, so that consumers' desire to shop is getting bigger and makes consumers feel happy to keep shopping on online shopping sites.
- Regarding privacy issues, the online store must provide a firm statement regarding the protection of consumer data privacy so that it is not misused, and carry out strict security for consumer data. Implement multiple layers of security and accommodate third parties to secure consumer data to keep it confidential.
- Regarding the issue of trust, the online shop must show that they can be trusted and honest. If the consumer's promise is not fulfilled, the online store can provide proper and reasonable compensation. The online store must also provide products whose quality can be accounted for and select their sellers well.
- Related to online shopping attitudes, online stores must make a unique differentiation with other shopping sites so that consumer attitudes will remain positive towards these shopping sites. Attractive offers and quite competitive product prices will also be able to improve consumer attitudes towards online shopping. Ease of shopping and transactions will also support the positive attitude of online store consumers so that the intention to do online shopping in the future will remain high.
- Related to online shopping intentions, the thing that needs to be done by the online store is to retain consumers to make repeat purchases in the future. Maintaining loyal customers is very necessary, because the costs incurred are not too large. For this reason, online stores must always have attractive shopping programs for their regular customers, so that they will continue to repurchase in the future. The online store can create a consumer loyalty scheme by providing bigger discounts for consumers who are longer regular customers.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

This research was supported in part by a grant from the Mahardhika School of Economics.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The Authors wish to declare that none has any interest to disclose.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

- [1] Pearson ML, Schell G. E-commerce Business Technology and Society 2008.
- [2] Parastanti GP. Pengaruh Prior Online Purchase Experience terhadap Trust dan Online Repurchase Intention (Survey pada Pelanggan ZALORA Indonesia Melalui Website www.zalora.co.id). *J Adm Bisnis* 2014;16.
- [3] Hanzaee KH, Rezaeyeh SP. Investigation of the effects of hedonic value and utilitarian value on customer satisfaction and behavioural intentions. *African J Bus Manag* 2013;7:818–25.
- [4] Yistiani NNM, Yasa NNM, Suasana IGA. Pengaruh atmosfer gerai dan pelayanan ritel terhadap nilai hedonik dan pembelian impulsif pelanggan matahari department store duta plaza di Denpasar. *J Manajemen, Strateg Bisnis, Dan Kewirausahaan* 2012;6:139–49.
- [5] Ho THL, Chen Y. Vietnamese consumers' intention to use online shopping: the role of trust. *Int J Bus Manag* 2014;9:145.
- [6] Soegiarto TA. Analisis pengaruh trust in online store, perceived risk, attitude towards online purchasing terhadap minat beli konsumen produk fashion di Surabaya. *Kaji Ilm Mhs Manaj* 2012;1.
- [7] Nulufi K. Minat Beli sebagai Mediasi Pengaruh Brand Image dan Sikap Konsumen terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Batik di Pekalongan (Studi Kasus pada Konsumen International Batik Center dan Pasar Grosir Setono) 2015.
- [8] Subagio H. Pengaruh atribut supermarket terhadap motif belanja hedonik motif belanja utilitarian dan loyalitas konsumen. *J Manaj Pemasar* 2012;6:8–21.
- [9] Blythe J. *Essentials of Marketing*. 3rd Editon. Harlow Pearson Educ Ltd 2005.
- [10] Andersson M, Prevedan T, Palmblad S. Atmospheric effects on hedonic and utilitarian customers 2012.
- [11] Kim H-S. Using hedonic and utilitarian shopping motivations to profile inner city consumers. *J Shopp Cent Res* 2006;13:57–79.
- [12] Flavián C, Guinalfú M. Consumer trust, perceived security and privacy policy: three basic elements of loyalty to a web site. *Ind Manag Data Syst* 2006.
- [13] Roca JC, García JJ, De La Vega JJ. The importance of perceived trust, security and privacy in online trading systems. *Inf Manag Comput Secur* 2009.
- [14] Armesh H, Salarzahi H, Yaghoobi NM, Heydari A, Nikbin D. The effects of security and privacy information on trust & trustworthiness and loyalty in online marketing in Malaysia. *Int J Mark Stud* 2010;2:223.
- [15] Mowen JC, Minor M. *Perilaku Konsumen dialih bahasakan oleh Dwi Kartika Yahya*. Jakarta: Erlangga 2012.
- [16] Schiffman L, Kanuk LL. *Perilaku konsumen edisi ketujuh*. Jakarta Indeks 2008.
- [17] Kotler P, Armstrong G. *Prinsip-prinsip pemasaran*. vol. 12. edisi; 2008.
- [18] Sumarwan U. *Perilaku konsumen*. Bogor Ghalia Indones 2011.
- [19] Arista D, Astuti SRT. Analisis pengaruh iklan, kepercayaan merek, dan citra merek terhadap minat beli konsumen. *J Ilm Aset* 2011;13:37–45.
- [20] Haekal A, Widjajanta B. Pengaruh kepercayaan dan persepsi risiko terhadap minat membeli secara online pada pengunjung website classifieds di inonesia. *J Bus Manag Educ* 2016;1:183–95.
- [21] Sugiyono D. *Metode penelitian pendidikan pendekatan kuantitatif, kualitatif dan R&D* 2013.
- [22] Hair Jr JF, Hult GTM, Ringle CM, Sarstedt M. *A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM)*. Sage publications; 2021.
- [23] Ghozali I. *Aplikasi analisis multivariate dengan program IBM SPSS 25* 2018.